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Legal Basis of Inclusive Education and its Implementation

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***Abstract:** This article discusses the legal basis of Inclusive Education and the issues of its implementation.*

***Keywords:** Inclusive Education, Rights, Obligations, Society, Discrimination, Disability, Concept.*

Today, a number of legal norms are being implemented in our country to reform education. In particular, the issues of educating children with special educational needs, adapting them to society, and involving them in the Inclusive Education system are becoming relevant. The issue of transitioning to an Inclusive Education system has been rapidly implemented in recent years. In this process, the issue of preparing educational entities for inclusive education and introducing conditions for inclusive education is becoming a priority.

In Uzbekistan, a number of works are being carried out to improve the system of state support for people with disabilities, medical and social assistance, improving the quality of life, and providing them with comprehensive assistance in obtaining education and employment. Taking into account the feelings of compassion and kindness inherent in our people, special attention is being paid to the important needs and requirements of people with disabilities. Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 “On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, No. PF-5270 dated December 1, 2017 “On measures to radically improve the system of state support for persons with disabilities”, No. PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019 “On the Concept of Development of the Public Education System until 2030”, No. PF-6108 dated November 6, 2020 “On measures to develop the spheres of education and science in the new period of development of Uzbekistan”, No. PQ-4860 dated October 13, 2020 “On the system of education for children with special educational needs It is important to implement the tasks set out in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 638 dated October 12, 2021 “On approval of regulatory legal acts on education of children with special educational needs”, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 “On the

Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”, and other regulatory legal acts related to this activity.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3931 dated September 5, 2018 “On measures to introduce new principles of management in the public education system” sets out specific tasks to further increase the effectiveness of measures to ensure social guarantees for children with special educational needs, to create an adaptive environment conducive to their education (including inclusive education).

Also, the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019, provides for improving the quality of educational services provided to children with special educational needs:

Development and approval of requirements for the premises of educational institutions where children with special educational needs receive education;

implementation of measures aimed at providing educational institutions with children with special educational needs with the necessary literature, methodological manuals, equipment and supplies for training in various professions;

organization of an inclusive education system for the education of children with special educational needs, provision of general education institutions with special devices (lifting devices, ramps, handrails, etc.), as well as relevant personnel (special educators, specialists in psychological and pedagogical observation of children);

carrying out explanatory work among the public about the right of children with special educational needs to receive education, the content and essence of inclusive education;

optimization of educational institutions with children with special educational needs, based on the physical and mental needs of students and the geographical location of educational institutions;

gradual provision of boarding schools with special equipment for the adaptation and integration of children with special educational needs;

Tasks have been set, such as implementing measures aimed at ensuring the right to inclusive education for every child with special educational needs.

“A draft of basic regulatory requirements for a modern school has been developed, which includes the creation of necessary conditions for the education of children with special educational needs, the construction of modern schools for them and the provision of equipment, along with special infrastructure. In addition, the provision of comprehensive assistance by educational institutions to children with special educational needs and their parents in receiving corrective pedagogical assistance and vocational guidance is stipulated in the Regulation “On the Procedure for Organizing Inclusive Education in General Secondary Education Organizations”, approved by Resolution No. 638 of the Cabinet of Ministers of October 12, 2021.¹

It is a matter of great importance to further improve the legal framework for corrective educational work with children with disabilities.

¹ Inklyuziv Ta’lim: nazariya va amaliyot. Qodirova Feruzaxon Usmonovna. Chirchiq 2022.12-13betlar.

Children in need of assistance with physical or mental disabilities are equal members of our state. Ensuring their education and upbringing in all institutions of the continuous education system is one of our main tasks.

Changing people's attitudes towards people with disabilities, informing others about their full and equal participation in society is of paramount importance in solving the urgent problems of people with disabilities. It is also gratifying to see the elimination of the concept of "disabled" from circulation and the introduction of the universally recognized term "person with disabilities", taking into account, first of all, the human nature of the person, and the organization of practical measures to prepare for the ratification of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child" guarantees the right of every child to be raised in his own family, determines the state policy on the protection of children's rights, and determines the guarantees of state bodies to ensure the rights of the child.

The "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" adopted by the UN in 1948 specifically recognizes that "Education is the fundamental and inalienable right of every person." Since the "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" guarantees the rights and freedoms of all people, it was determined that all the provisions of this Declaration also apply to people with special needs. In order to further strengthen and guarantee the rights of persons with disabilities, the UN adopted the "Declaration on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities" in 1975.

The Declaration states:

"Persons with disabilities are born with the right to respect for their dignity. Regardless of the origin, nature and severity of their disability, they have the same rights as other citizens of their age, including the right to a full and decent life as possible" (Declaration on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, Article 3).

Similarly, to protect the rights of children, the UN adopted the Convention on the Rights of the Child in 1989. The Convention on the Rights of the Child is an international human rights treaty designed to protect the rights of children everywhere. It has been ratified by almost all countries in the world. The 191 countries that have ratified the Convention have voluntarily undertaken to implement the provisions of the Convention on the Rights of the Child through administrative legislation, judicial and other measures. The Convention on the Rights of the Child is the only Convention that covers such complex and multifaceted aspects as civil, political, economic, social and cultural.

It is necessary to find an opportunity to identify all children with disabilities early and involve them in education. On the basis of all the above-mentioned legal and regulatory documents and international conferences, children with special needs are recognized as full, equal members of society, and a new approach to their education has emerged. These forms of education are called inclusive and integrated education.

The content of the declaration is that it is determined that the rights of persons with disabilities and their opportunities for education are protected by all states.²

In this regard, R.A. Suleymenova expressed the opinion that: "If children with disabilities are denied the opportunity to participate in the social life of their communities and society as a whole, their opportunities will be sharply reduced."

² Inklyuziv Ta'lim:nazariya va amaliyot. Qodirova Feruzaxon Usmanovna. Chirchiq 2022. 14-16-betlar.

“Continuity of education is the key to the new global economy. Education is of fundamental importance for development, social progress and human freedom,” she emphasizes.

In order to ensure the right of every child with disabilities to live and be raised in their own family, general, that is, inclusive education, has been established as a priority form of education. This education allows children with disabilities to live in a family, enjoy parental love and receive education among their peers in their neighborhood.

Since the “Convention on the Rights of the Child” guarantees all the rights of children with special needs, the principle of “all rights for all children” is recognized.

In this regard, the Convention on the Rights of the Child states in relation to the education of children with special needs: “Education, which is a means of identifying the special needs of a child with disabilities and leading to his or her integration into social life and development as a person, should be provided with comprehensive assistance.” According to this law, it is of great importance for children with special needs to fully participate in the life of society, grow up in harmony with national beliefs and culture, and contribute to the development of society by enjoying all its beauty and richness.

A child receiving separate education limits his or her socialization, underdevelops his or her knowledge base, and at the same time makes it difficult for him or her to be prepared for life. Integrated, inclusive education has long been a pressing human rights issue. Many children still prefer to be educated in special Internet settings, where their parents believe that there are favorable conditions for the child. However, adults with disabilities, describing themselves as having experienced inclusive education, are demanding the abolition of separate education. Because "after leaving a comfortable, privileged environment, where everything is ready, the struggle to adapt and find one's place will last for many years."³ The Convention on the Rights of the Child is a comprehensive and multifaceted instrument, the only one that guarantees all children the civil, political, economic, social and cultural aspects of human rights.

This Convention is binding. It calls on all governments to take steps to protect the rights of all children. It is also comprehensive because it states that all rights are inalienable, interdependent and equal. Article 2 of the Convention states that “No child shall be subjected to any form of discrimination on the part of his or her parents or legal guardians, irrespective of their race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national, ethnic or social origin, property, birth or other status.” It is Article 28, entitled “Education is a human political right”, which states that States Parties recognize the right of all children to education and, with a view to achieving this right progressively and on the basis of equal opportunity, shall make primary education free and compulsory. This article also states that children with special needs should receive education and that education should be compulsory for them.

As a result, a very important World Conference was held in Thailand in 1990. At this conference, the World Declaration on “Education for All” was adopted. This Declaration adopted the following statement: “Schools are characterized not by the capabilities of children, but by the quality of their work and the responsiveness of school education. They consist of the following:

- the right of every child to receive education in a public school;
- the methods and techniques of teaching are selected depending on the child's disability;
- the school provides full-fledged corrective pedagogical assistance;

³ N.B.Goipova.Inklyuziv Ta’lim.Gospital Pedagogika.Namangan 2024. 76-b.

- decisions on children are made in a comprehensive manner;
- each individual right of the child is guaranteed;
- the principle of integration in schools is considered the basis of the curriculum;
- the material support of inclusive schools is improved".

In order to implement the goals of "Education for All" and ensure that children with special needs receive a full-fledged education, it was determined that on June 7-10, 1994, with the support of the Spanish state and UNESCO, the "Second World Conference on Special Needs" was held in Salamanca (Spain). This Conference was called the "Salamanca Declaration and Framework for the Further Implementation of the Education of Children with Special Needs", and its work was published in the same year under the title "Salamanca Statement and Plan of Action". This document sets out the ideas that illuminate the content of the rights declarations. The main guiding principle of the Salamanca Statement and Plan of Action is that schools should accommodate all children, regardless of their physical, mental, social, emotional, linguistic and other characteristics. This document states:

"Every child has the right to education and to the attainment of knowledge at a level appropriate to his or her level:

- The education system and educational programs should be adjusted to take into account different characteristics and needs and should be directed towards this. Children with special needs should be given the opportunity to attend regular schools;
- Since working with children with special needs is part of the work of regular schools, this process can be the most effective means of achieving the following goals:

Combating the scourge of exclusion;

Creating friendly humane communities, building a society that includes people with special needs;

Achieving education for all children" (Salamanca Declaration, paragraph 2);

The Salamanca Declaration and Plan of Action put forward the slogan "Education for all". "Education for all" means that children with disabilities or from marginalized groups in society should receive education on an equal basis.

The analysis of this action plan shows that the main principle underlying it is the following:

"Schools should be inclusive of all children, regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic or other disabilities. This includes children with mental and physical disabilities, homeless children, children belonging to nomadic peoples, and children from families with ethnic or cultural disadvantages" (Introduction to the Action Plan, paragraph 3).

The Salamanca Declaration and Action Plan specifically emphasize the need for inclusive education for children with special needs within the general education system, emphasizing that each child has unique needs and that each child has the right to attend a school close to where they live.

The main goal of such schools is not only to provide effective education to all children, but also to create a society that is inclusive and welcoming towards children with special needs and to eliminate discriminatory changes.⁴

⁴ Inklyuziv ta'lim. L.R.Muminova. R.SH. Shomaxmudova. Z.M.Ahmedova. Toshkent 2019. 38-40 betlar.

In conclusion, the implementation of inclusive education depends not only on providing effective education to all healthy and disabled children, but also on their ability to take their place in society in a way that is suitable and convenient for all. If each teacher implements educational activities purposefully, taking into account the level of physical development of the students, we will undoubtedly achieve the goals we have set for ourselves.

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